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WP2– Foundations

D2.6 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v2

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BIML	Building Information Management Layer
CA	Certificate Authority
DIML	District Information Management Layer
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IANA	Internet Assigned Numbers Authority
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MitM	Man in the Middle
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
SEAC	SEcurity Access Control
SSH	Secure SHell
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WAN	Wide Area Network
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is one of the deliverables of the ACCEPT project, under WP2 – Foundations, and in particular, task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers. The purpose of this deliverable is to give a detailed description of the final cybersecurity framework as it has been designed in agreement with the system architecture. A lot of attention has been given to the protection of the personal data of the users throughout the whole platform. All mechanisms and principles followed are designed with respect to General Data Protection Regulation. All data that are being processed inside the ACCEPT platform have been anonymized, while security mechanisms have been implemented in all components of the platform, to protect the end user's privacy. A risk assessment has been completed by relevant partners to achieve a clear view of the potential risks and threats, and to plan the proper countermeasures to eliminate them. Finally, this deliverable describes the specific security mechanisms that were finally chosen and incorporated in the ACCEPT platform, following the previous version the Deliverable D2.5-Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v1.

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Scope of the deliverable

The main scope of this deliverable is to describe in detail the second and final version of Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines of the ACCEPT platform and mainly the anonymization techniques proposed, the Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) conducted, and the mechanisms applied to protect the information flow. As described in the previous version of this deliverable, in the context of **Task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers** of **WP2 – Foundations**, potential security risks were taken into consideration and were evaluated in accordance with the current General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This version aims to present the security measures that were taken to mitigate the possible threats, as well as to give a clear view of the re-evaluated risk after the security framework was followed.

The security framework designed can be categorized in the above 5 fields:

- Risk Assessment
- Anonymization Techniques
- Communications Protection
- Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Blockchain security
- Web App Security

Each of these aspects will be analyzed both in terms of technical details and security contribution to the whole platform. The framework is implemented and aims to provide a platform that has its center on the protection of the private data, while it maintains high efficiency on its procedures. To achieve this, security has been considered throughout the complete information flow. In this deliverable the complete and updated cybersecurity framework is presented, along with the detailed result from the DPIA assessment described in the previous version of this deliverable D2.5 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & Specifications for data protection & privacy v1.

1.2. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

T2.4 Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers along with deliverables D2.5 and its upgraded version D2.6 are part of Work Package 2, WP2 – foundations, and have close ties to the activities of other tasks in the same WP, as well as their respective deliverables. T2.1 – Market actor & Prosumer requirement & Business scenario definition, and deliverable D2.1 – Business scenarios, use cases & requirements, in which the use cases examined are analyzed, and T2.3 – System architecture design, configuration & elaboration, and deliverable D2.3 – system architecture description v1 (due in M10), in which the system architecture is described. Security mechanisms are an important aspect of the overall system architecture since they are created to safeguard the system from harmful cyberattacks and to provide users with a safe experience while maintaining high service functioning. The system architecture and the overall security design are inextricably linked. Since it specifies the essential security architecture, the findings of this deliverable serve as an input for Task T4.1-Smart Home IoT solution description & Building Information Management Layer setup. The interdependencies of WP2 and Work Packages are depicted in Figure 1, below.

Figure 1 Work Packages Interdependencies

Figure 2 WP2 Tasks interdependencies.

1.3. Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable consists of six chapters that are structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the objectives and the scope of the deliverable, its structure and its relation to the other tasks.
- **Chapter 2** discusses the results of the Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) that were circulated among the pilots.
- **Chapter 3** includes the technical and structural details the Peer-to-Peer Security Framework.
- **Chapter 4** presents the procedures followed to anonymize and secure the processed data and describes the communications which take place within the platform.
- **Chapter 5** presents the authentication flow that was adopted for the citizen app and,
- **Chapter 6** provides a summary as well as the conclusions of this Deliverable

2. Data Privacy Impact Assessment Results

As described in the previous version of this deliverable, the assessment conducted is based on the Regulatory Recommendations for Privacy, Data Protection and Cyber-Security in the Data Protection Impact Assessment Template for Smart Grid and Smart Metering [1]. The assessment document presented also in the previous version of this Deliverable, was circulated among the partners that are responsible for components that process data across the whole platform. As the flow of data did not present any major differentiation among the different use cases and pilots, contrary to previous estimations a universal assessment was conducted for the complete platform functionalities. As can be seen in Figure 3, the three components that handle data coming from external sources, or in general have direct communication with third parties are the Building Information Management Layer (BIML), the District Information Management Layer (DIML) and the Citizen App. However, the data collected from the DIML component are not private and cannot be linked to data subjects. The rest of the data collected are completely anonymized as it is further analysed in section 4. For these reasons, the DPIA was directed to the technical partners responsible for these components (QUE, Hypertech and CERTH). More specifically, there were 2 sheets disseminated, each one representing the data flow from the BAM to the Citizen App, and the flow from the BIML to the Citizen App, respectively. Since only those three ACCEPT components handle private data the analysis has been focused on those. The rest of the components do not have access to private data, rather they process already anonymized or encrypted ones. A comparative presentation of the assessment performed before the implementation of the security measures, and then again after the establishment of the security framework is presented in this section.

For further details on the separate steps followed on the DPIA conduct, the reader may also consult the previous version of this deliverable D2.5 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & Specifications for data protection & privacy v1 [2]

2.1. Steps followed for the ACCEPT platform DPIA

In this section, the steps followed to conduct the DPIA, are presented. CERTH, having the role of the task leader, lead and supervised the whole process.

- An internal meeting was organized, to share guidelines along with an excel sheet template,
- All related partners were asked to complete the DPIA report, while CERTH provided assistance when it was requested,
- CERTH managed and merged given feedback to a single DPIA document, to form the universal assessment,
- After studying upon the DPIA findings, CERTH proposed mitigation measures to address possible risks,
- The DPIA was completed by re-assessing the Risk Level after the countermeasures were taken under consideration,
- The Final Results are reported in this deliverable, and they are also disseminated among related partners.

Figure 3 Accept high-level system architecture

2.2. Assessment and results

The DPIA report details how the chosen (completed or planned) controls relate to certain Risks and shows that they result in tolerable risk levels. When completing the DPIA and a specific risk is shared, a Data Controller also specifies which control actions has implemented, or plans to implement, to mitigate the risk. Organizations can use the (DPIA) to take appropriate steps to mitigate the risks of their pilot site and, as a result, the possible impact of the risks on data subjects, non-compliance risk, legal action risk, and operational risk. For further information about these types of risks, see Table 1. The identification of assets and actors in which personal data is stored is a crucial step in determining the dangers that threaten the system. By undertaking threat assessment and risk evaluation, all related partners were able to identify strategies and implement controls to reduce their risk to acceptable levels.

Table 1 Risk Types

Type of Risk	Definition
Non-compliance risk	"An organization's potential exposure to legal penalties, financial forfeiture and material loss, resulting from its failure to act in accordance with industry laws and regulations, internal policies or prescribed best practices" [3]
Legal action risk	"The likelihood of financial or reputational loss resulting from a lack of knowledge (or misunderstanding) of how the law applies to your business, or operating with a reckless indifference to the law and how it applies" [4]
Operational risk	"The risk of a change in value caused by the fact that actual losses, incurred for inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems, or from external events (including legal risk), differ from the expected losses" [5]

In this section, there is a comparative presentation of the risk level before and after implementing some security measures. It is evident that after identifying the possible threats and adopting respective risk treatments both the severity and likelihood of each threat category has decreased in acceptable levels, both in the case of BAM-C-App and BIML-C-App. The ANNEX I and II include the completed DPIA files for the two flows (BAM - C-App and BIML - C-App), while ANNEX III and IV include the description for the Threats affecting Assets and the Severity & Likelihood Scale, respectively. For each case, three diagrams are presented:

- The first one depicts, a comparative analysis per threat category, in terms of Severity and Likelihood, before and after the control actions have been implemented (Figure 4, Figure 7)
- The second and third diagrams depict the Risk level per threat, as it is calculated as a function of the Likelihood and the Severity of threats, again before and after the control actions have been implemented. Furthermore, the last two diagrams are accompanied with the tables that describe the final Risk level calculation (Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 8, Figure 9)

Further details concerning the DPIA documents, are included in the previous version of this deliverable [2].

2.2.1. BAM – C-App DPI Assessment

The results of the DPIA assessment in terms of Likelihood and Severity levels per Threat Category, initially and after the control actions for the BAM – C-App data flow, are presented in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Table 2 Initial Severity, Likelihood and Risk Level (BAM-C-App)

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)	Severity at TC Level	Likelihood at TC Level	Initial Risk Level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	4	4	1
Inadequate information of the data subject	2	3	3
Violation of the data subject's rights	4	2	2
Compliance violations in the contracts	0	1	4
Personal Data integrity loss	3	3	3
Damage to individual	0	1	4

Table 3 Residual Severity, Likelihood and Risk Level (BAM-C-App)

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)	Residual Severity at TC level	Residual Likelihood at TC Level	Residual Risk Level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	4	2	2
Inadequate information of the data subject	2	2	4
Violation of the data subject's rights	3	2	2
Compliance violations in the contracts	0	1	4
Personal Data integrity loss	3	2	2
Damage to individual	0	1	4

These results are also depicted in a Kiviat diagram in Figure 4, as well as a plane diagram for the initial and residual Risk Level in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 4 Severity & Likelihood vs Residual Severity & Likelihood – BAM – C-App

Figure 5 Initial Risk Level – BAM – C-App

Figure 6 Residual Risk Level – BAM – C-App

As shown in the figures below the DPIA conducted for the BAM-C-App flow, the Residual Likelihood is significantly decreased for all possible threat categories, after the control actions. As far as the overall Risk Level is concerned, there is no threat category depicted in the red area that represents the maximum risk. Furthermore, the control actions achieved risk mitigation for all threat categories.

2.2.2. BIML – C-App DPI Assessment

The results of the DPIA assessment in terms of Likelihood and Severity levels per Threat Category, initially and after the control actions for the BIML – C-App data flow, are presented in Table 4 and Table 5, respectively.

Table 4 Initial Severity, Likelihood and Risk Level (BIML-C-App)

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)	Severity at TC Level	Likelihood at TC Level	Initial Risk Level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	4	4	1
Inadequate information of the data subject	1	1	4
Violation of the data subject's rights	3	2	2
Compliance violations in the contracts	2	2	4
Personal Data integrity loss	3	3	3
Damage to individual	4	3	2

Table 5 Residual Severity, Likelihood and Risk Level (BIML-C-App)

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)	Residual Severity at TC level	Residual Likelihood at TC Level	Residual Risk Level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	1	1	4
Inadequate information of the data subject	1	1	4
Violation of the data subject's rights	1	1	4
Compliance violations in the contracts	1	1	4
Personal Data integrity loss	1	1	4
Damage to individual	2	2	4

These results are also depicted in a Kiviat diagram in Figure 7, as well as a plane diagram for the initial and residual Risk Level in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 7 Severity & Likelihood vs Residual Severity & Likelihood – BIML – C-App

Figure 8 Initial Risk Level – BIML – C-App

Figure 9 Residual Risk Level – BIML – C-App

The results for the BIML-C-App flow have shown a great improvement on the overall Likelihood levels, which is also depicted in the Residual Risk Level diagram. In addition, there is no threat category at the red area or maximum risk level after the control actions have been taken into consideration.

3. Peer-to-Peer Security Framework

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Platform is based on blockchain technology and is build using the Cosmos and Tendermint frameworks. Blockchain is one of the most secure data protection technologies, and the core concept is to keep the data in a distributed ledger. The participants of a blockchain network have the permission to write, read and verify recorded transactions, but they are not allowed to delete or modify anything that has already been stored in the distributed ledger.

Records of data in the P2P Platform follow the typical block structure that is common to every blockchain framework. This attribute offers immutability since it creates a chain of digital blocks that each one contains records of transactions. Every block that is created holds energy and flexibility transactions together with the Smart Contract results is linked to the previous one, and the new one will be placed after it. This makes it almost impossible to tamper with the already stored data, since the malicious attacker would not only need to change the block with the specific entries but also all the blocks that were created after that to avoid detection.

Having to change multiple records at once instead of a single entry might not sound as a major deteriorating factor, however P2P offers an additional security layer. Cryptography is an inherent characteristic of blockchain technology. Community members will hold a pair of keys, a private and public that will be used as a personal digital signature. Both will be kept at the digital wallet of the user. The private key will be used by the user to sign every transaction that will be transmitted and stored on the blockchain network, and the public key will be used to confirm that that the message was truly sent by the specific user. The public key of a community member can also be the digital identity of the user as it necessary for verifying digital signature, and it is a common practice for managing user's identity without revealing real world identity. Therefore, to maliciously alter one or many inputs from a blockchain network the signature will be invalid, and the network will immediately identify the threat.

The P2P Platform as a decentralized and blockchain powered platform will inherently be decentralized and distributed across all the community members. The community members will be responsible to continuously update and keep in sync using their private and public keys. Therefore, the database does not have a single point of failure since it is not located in a specific area. However, malicious or failing machines could in theory affect the blockchain network. The Tendermint Core, the low-level consensus and networking protocol, that lies on the foundation of the P2P Platform utilizes Byzantine Fault Tolerant consensus algorithm. Practically the network can operate unobscured even if 2/3 of the peers are offline, or act maliciously.

4. Anonymization of the Private Data and Securing of Data in Transit

In this section, there are detailed information on the procedures followed for the anonymization of the private data, and the measures taken to protect the communications that take place between the components of the platform. In order to better understand the information handling and flow, Figure 3 summarizes the ACCEPT high-level system architecture as it was presented in Deliverable 2.3 - ACCEPT system architecture description v1.

4.1. End Users Anonymization

As mention in section 2, private data are handled by the BIML and BAM, while the C-App is the component that interacts with the end-users (components inside green frames in the figure). In other words, these components are the only ones that have access to data outside the ACCEPT platform. This is a crucial point concerning the protection and security of the whole information flow in the platform. As it is also described in the previous version of this deliverable, it is important that any connection between the data subject and their actual personal information should be eliminated. The initial framework proposal suggested using homomorphic encryption in order to achieve this anonymity of the users (reader may consult the previous version of the deliverable [2]). However, as the system architecture progressed, the policy followed has changed, due to the fact that the anonymity of the users is now handled before their data are inputted inside the ACCEPT platform.

In detail, once the pilot partners install the proper equipment in the end users' personal area, they are assigning to them a Universally Unique IDentifier (UUID). UUID is a 128-bit label used in computer systems to identify information. Also known as a Globally Unique IDentifier (GUID) [6]. When produced using the standard methods, UUIDs are, in practice, unique. Unlike most other numbering schemes, their uniqueness is not dependent on a central registration body or cooperation between the parties creating them. While the likelihood of a UUID being copied is not zero, it is near enough to be insignificant [7] [8]. As a result, anyone may generate a UUID and use it to identify something with a high degree of assurance that the identifier does not duplicate one that has previously been or will be generated to identify something else. Information identified with UUIDs by separate parties may thus be integrated into a single database or communicated over the same channel with a minimal chance of duplication.

Taking under consideration the techniques that are available for anonymizing data, as described in the previous version of this deliverable, the procedure followed belongs to the Pseudonymization. The technique refers to the replacement of the data that act as key identifiers, with aliases also known as "pseudonyms". It can be both, a reversible and non-reversible process. In the current context, the UUIDs play the role of the pseudonyms, and the process can be reversible only in the site of the pilot partners.

This UUID is the only identifier that is available inside the ACCEPT platform. There is no other personal information describing the end user, communicated to the system. Hence, it is not possible to link any data subject with their corresponding information. Consequently, the anonymity is preserved. Implementing a homomorphic algorithm to the data exchanged between the platform components, would cause additional computational complexity, while at the same time the purpose of anonymity is already served. Furthermore, the final framework has an enhanced level of security as there are practically no personal information being handled on any component, included the citizen web application. In section 5, there is an extend presentation on the way that a user registers and logs in the app without providing any additional personal information, besides the UUID, as well as a description of the way that the pilot partners contribute to these procedures.

4.2. Network and Communications Protection

As described in the previous section, the data that are exchanged inside the ACCEPT platform are completely anonymized and there are no components that stores any private data. However, it is still important that the communications that take place inside the platform stay secure. In the security framework designed, all communications are encrypted. In this section the security mechanisms/algorithms applied for such purposes are presented.

4.2.1. Internal communications between the platform components

All data that are exchanged between the components in the ACCEPT platform are encrypted with the use of the HTTPS protocol. HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) is a secure alternative of the HTTP protocol that

encrypts and authenticates data using the SSL/TLS protocol. RFC 2818 [9] specifies HTTPS, which by default utilizes port 443 instead of HTTP's port 80. The HTTPS protocol allows transmitting sensitive information across the internet in a safe manner. HTTPS enhances the HTTP protocol by adding encryption. HTTP is prone to eavesdropping and Man in the Middle attacks¹ since it was initially built as a clear text protocol. HTTPS protects data transferred over the internet from being intercepted and read by a third party by using SSL/TLS encryption. An encrypted communication session can be safely established between two parties (e.g., a web server and browser), via the generation of a shared secret key using public-key cryptography and the SSL/TLS handshake. In terms of authentication, unlike HTTP, HTTPS uses the SSL/TLS protocol to provide secure authentication. A client can utilize the public key in an SSL/TLS certificate to verify that documents supplied by the server (such as HTML pages) have been digitally signed by someone who has the associated private key. The client will accept that any identifying information provided in the certificate has been validated by a trusted third party if the server's certificate has been signed by a publicly trustworthy certificate authority (CA). Finally, HTTPS contributes also to the data integrity. Each document (such as a web page, image, or JavaScript file) sent to a browser by an HTTPS web server includes a digital signature that a web browser can use to determine that the document has not been altered by a third party or otherwise corrupted while in transit. The server calculates a cryptographic hash of the document's contents, included with its digital certificate, which the browser can independently calculate to prove that the document's integrity is intact.

In case another protocol is used, in specific Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), the communication is again protected through the use of Transport Layer Security (TLS). The Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) transport protocol is used by MQTT. TCP connections do not employ encrypted communication by default. Many MQTT brokers support the use of TLS instead of plain TCP to encrypt the whole MQTT transaction. When the MQTT CONNECT packet's username and password fields are used for authentication and permission, TLS is strongly recommended. "Secure-MQTT" is the standardized name at Internet Assigned Numbers Authority (IANA) [10]. MQTT over TLS uses port 8883, which is dedicated especially for it.

4.2.2. Protection of physical/virtual components

External access to the available components (when possible) has an additional level of protection. More specifically, the DIML component, as illustrated in Figure 3, is a virtual component installed on CIRCE servers. Access to these servers is only permitted via Secure Shell (SSH). SSH is a network protocol that allows users, especially system administrators, to access a computer across an insecure network in a secure manner [11]. The SSH protocol is also implemented by a set of tools known as SSH. SSH also allows for robust password and public key authentication, as well as encrypted data exchange between two computers connected over an open network like the internet. SSH is commonly used by network administrators to manage systems and programs remotely, allowing them to log in to another computer via a network, execute commands, and move data from one machine to another, in addition to offering robust encryption. Both the cryptographic network protocol and the set of programs that implement it are referred to as SSH. The client-server architecture is used by SSH, which connects a Secure Shell client program, which displays the session, with an SSH server, which operates the session. Application protocols for terminal emulation and file transfers are frequently supported by SSH implementations. By default, an SSH server listens on port 22 of the TCP.

In addition, the security is enhanced due to another restriction. In order for someone to be able to establish an SSH connection, they must first connect to the Virtual Private Network (VPN) established. A VPN extends a private network across a public network, allowing users to transmit and receive data as if their computers were physically linked to the private network [12]. Increased functionality, security, and control of the private network are all advantages of using a VPN. It is frequently used by distant employees to gain access to resources that are not available on the public network. Although encryption is broadly used, it is not required for a VPN connection. A VPN is formed by using dedicated circuits or tunneling techniques to build a virtual point-to-point connection over existing networks. Some of the benefits of a wide area network can be obtained using a VPN accessible over the public Internet (WAN). The resources provided within the private network can be accessed remotely from the user's perspective.

¹ Man in the Middle (MitM) attack is a type of cyberattack in which the attacker silently redirects and perhaps modifies messages between two parties who believe they are interacting directly with each other because the attacker has positioned themselves between them.

5. Citizen App: User Registration and Authentication

This section contains information regarding the procedure followed to register and authenticate an end-user in the citizen web app. As described in section 4, the pilot-partners do not share any information concerning the personal identity of the end-users. Thus, the challenge that is brought up regards the fact that there is no way to match a legitimate user with an identifier such as a personal email, as according to the GDPR [13] emails are classified in the Personally Identifiable Information (PII) list. The PII is any piece of data that may be used alone or in combination with other data to identify a physical person. Some indicative examples of PII are:

- Name and Surname
- Social Security Number
- Address
- Phone Number
- Email
- Birthday

The Figure 10 depicts the different categories that the data classifies as a PII lie in. PII might be classified as sensitive or non-sensitive. Non-sensitive PII is information that may be transferred in plain text without causing harm to the individual. Non-sensitive PII is widely accessible through public records, phone books, company directories, and websites. This might contain information such as zip code, race, gender, date of birth, and religion – information that could not be used to determine an individual's identity on its own. Sensitive PII is information that, if released, might cause harm to the individual in the event of a data breach. This sort of sensitive material frequently has legal, contractual, or ethical restrictions on dissemination. Sensitive PII should thus be encrypted both in transit and at rest. This category contains also digital account information such as email addresses.

Figure 10 GDPR Personal Data [14]

In order to design a secure and efficient registration/authentication flow for the citizen app, there should be a factor that could identify an individual as a legitimate user of the ACCEPT system, without asking them for further personal information. As it is also mentioned in section 4.1 this piece of information is the UUID given by the pilot partners

that install the equipment in the end-users' site. To proceed with the registration, the Citizen App should have access to a list with all valid UUIDs. In the subsection following there is a step-by-step procedure description.

5.1. Phase 1: UUID and password granting and storing

When an energy provider installs the equipment on a user's site and registers them as a client, they also assign to them a one-time password. The pair of username (UUID) and password is recorded to a table, which contains the list of all the users registered accompanied with their valid passwords. This list is shared with the Citizen app. It is very important to clarify that while the UUIDs are stored in plain-text, their corresponding passwords are encrypted. For that purpose, a hashing algorithm is implemented. According to [15], approximately 53% of internet users use a single password on the majority of websites. In other words, if a password is stored in plain text and the database/server that it is stored in is attacked, the hacker may obtain access not just to this specific account, but also to multiple accounts. Therefore, the password should not be available in plain-text.

To overcome this problem, as already mentioned the passwords should be kept encrypted. However, applying a simple encryption algorithm is still not secure. Encryption processes are consistently reversible and give one-to-one mapping from input and output and vice versa. An attacker has the ability to decipher the passwords if he obtains the encryption key. A one-way cryptographic hash algorithm might be a superior option. The hash function creates a many-to-one mapping between input and output, making reversing an output very hard (Figure 11). Collisions occur when for different input values to a hashing algorithm result in the same hash output. Because of the pigeonhole principle, collisions are unavoidable. The pigeonhole principle asserts that if n items are placed in m containers with $n > m$, at least one container must hold more than one item [16]. In accordance with a hash function, If there are n objects in a set, and n is bigger than $|R|$, which in this instance is the range of the hash value, the chance of a hash collision is 1, implying that it will happen [17]. Collisions are rarer in a competent cryptographic hash function. When hashing passwords, it is safe to expect that the hash function will provide unique results, meaning that no two passwords will have the same hash value.

Figure 11 Irreversible Hash Functions

In the context of the ACCEPT platform, password will be stored using the SHA-256 algorithm. SHA-256 [18] is an iterated cryptographic hash algorithm based on a compression function that modifies the state of eight 32-bit chaining variables A, B, \dots, H depending on the contents of the message's 16 32-bit words $M_0 \dots M_{15}$. Figure 12 shows the compression function, which is made up of 64 similar stages. Bitwise Boolean functions and 2 S-boxes, as shown below, are used in the step transformation.

$$Maj(A, B, C) = (A \wedge B) \vee (A \wedge C) \vee (B \wedge C)$$

$$Ch(E, F, G) = (E \wedge F) \vee (\neg E \wedge G)$$

$$\Sigma_0(x) = ROTR^2(x) \oplus ROTR^{13}(x) \oplus ROTR^{22}(x)$$

$$\Sigma_1(x) = ROTR^6(x) \oplus ROTR^{11}(x) \oplus ROTR^{25}(x)$$

Figure 12 SHA-256 Bitwise Functions and S-boxes

The S-boxes are made up of bitwise XORs \oplus and word rotations to the right (ROTR). The i -th step employs a constant K_i as well as the enlarged message's i -th word W_i .

Figure 13 A single step of the SHA-256 compression function

The messaging expansion process is further described. A 512-bit message block is created from an input message (after padding). The formula depicted in Figure 14 is used to create the words W_i from the initial message M . A single message block is represented as either a row vector $m \in Z_2^{512}$ or a vector M of 16 32-bit bits $M_t \in Z_{2^{32}}$, with $0 \leq i < 16$. This input is expanded into a vector of 64 32-bit words $W_i \in Z_{2^{32}}$ during message expansion, which may also be visualized as the 2048-bit expanded message row-vector w .

$$W_i = \begin{cases} M_i & \text{for } 0 \leq i < 16 \\ \sigma_1(W_{i-2}) + W_{i-7} + \sigma_0(W_{i-15}) + W_{i-16} & \text{for } 16 \leq i < N \end{cases}$$

Figure 14 Formula for message generation in SHA-256

If we set N to 64, we get conventional SHA-256; if we change N to a different number, we get a reduced (or extended) variation. The functions $\sigma_0(x) = ROTR^7(x) \oplus ROTR^{18}(x) \oplus SHR^3(x)$ and $\sigma_1(x) = ROTR^{17}(x) \oplus ROTR^{19}(x) \oplus 10(x)$ are S-boxes derived from rotations to the right (ROTR) and shifts to the right (SHR).

5.2. Phase 2: Registration on the Citizen App

When phase 1 is completed, users that want to register to the Citizen App, have their credentials. Additionally,, the Citizen App has access to the updated list with the UUID-Password pairs. So, the process of registration is executed as follows:

- The user connects to the Citizen web app for the first time
- They choose the option to register
- In the form that shows up, they should fill their UUID and the password that they were given by their provider
- The app then requests from the user to change their password, due to privacy issues (the provider should not know to the user's password after the registration)
- The shared list is updated with the new password

This procedure is simple and ensures that the UUID representing a user exist inside the ACCEPT platform. However, there is another issue that arises regarding authentication. User authentication refers to the process of verifying the identity of a user. In the steps described above, there is no way to actually verify that the person that wants to register and reset the password is the legitimate user that possesses the credentials given by the provider. To eliminate such risks, Multi-Factor Authentication is introduced. Multi-factor Authentication (MFA) refers to the process where a user that wants to be authenticated, should provide more than one verification factors. Therefore, the process becomes more secure as the likelihood of a successful cyber-attack is decreased. The aforementioned verification factors can be classified in the following three categories [60]:

- Possession or Something-You-Have. In order to get authorized you need to possess a device, like a smart card
- Knowledge or Something-You-Know. A PIN, password or an answer to a security question is required to proceed with the authentication
- Being or Something-You-Are. Biometric features such voice, face or fingerprint

The second factor that is asked from the user lies in the second category, Knowledge. A one-time password is sent to the user after they enter their credentials for the first time. Nevertheless, as stated before there should be no personal data of the users stored in the server/database of the Citizen app. To address this obstruction, the shared list between the citizen app and a pilot partner includes one more hashed value, the user's email. The steps of the procedure are now slightly modified:

- The user connects to the Citizen web app for the first time
- They choose the option to register
- In the form that shows up, they should fill their UUID and the password that they were given by their provider, along with their email
- The email is hashed, and the output is compared with the stored hashed email attribute in the list, for the corresponding user. If there is a match the procedure continues, else it is interrupted
- The app the asks the user to change their password, due to privacy issues (the provider should not know to the user's password after the registration)
- To confirm the password update, a one-time password is sent to the user's email, and then the plaintext email is rejected from the server.
- The user is asked to enter this OTP. If there is match the user is successfully logged in, else the procedure is interrupted
- The shared list is updated with the new password

This updated registration flow provides the Citizen app with an enhanced security level and at the same time it maintains the privacy and anonymity of the end-users by not storing any of their personal information. The hash function used for the email is once again the SHA-256 which was described in the previous section.

The MFA is only called during the registration phase. If a user wants to login after the registration, the UUID with their valid password are the only authenticators required. Only in case wants to reset/change the password the MFA is once again applied.

In Figure 15 the whole process of registration is depicted in a sequence diagram.

Figure 15 Registration Flow

6. Conclusions

This Deliverable is part of Task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers is part of WP2 – Foundations of the ACCEPT project. It provides a thorough and updated description of all the security mechanisms applied in the context of the ACCEPT security framework.

The deliverable described the process followed for the risk assessment performed via the DPIA, along with a comparative analysis of the risks existing before and after the implementation of the different security countermeasures. It also details the security mechanisms and policies that were implemented in the Peer-2-Peer Blockchain Exchange Platform component. The techniques applied to anonymise all data that are inputted into the platform are presented, along with the procedure followed to retain the individuality of the data through the use of the UUIDs. In addition, the document includes also the security mechanisms applied to protect the internal and external communications, as well as the virtual and physical components of the platform. Finally, there is a detailed presentation the registration flow designed especially for the ACCEPT Citizen App, in order to preserve the user's anonymity while also ensuring a secured access.

In summary, the main purpose of the framework was to give a complete solution for a fully anonymised data flow. This goal was accomplished through a detailed risk assessment, conducted universally. After acknowledging all possible threats, several security countermeasures and policies were designed and adopted, resulting in an elevated security level. All personal data were protected, with respect to the GDPR, as a consequence of the anonymization and encryption techniques applied.

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ANNEX I – DPIA (BAM-C-App)

Internal Team

DPIA will be performed by:	Option III	: the persons in charge of the application/system which is the target of the DPIA. This might especially apply in the case of SME's with limited resources.
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Actors & Assets

Asset	Actor Name (physical component)	Actor Type	Actor description (e.g. Where does Personal Data Processing Operations occur?)	How many data subjects for that Personal Data reside in each Actor instance?	Retention Time within Actor		Data Controller (physical person in the internal team)	Data Processor (physical person in the internal team)
					How long are they kept within the Actor?	How frequently are Personal Data accessed?		
DER_Measurements	Database	System	Cloud based component (ODFM)	All DERs at pilot sites	For as long as the optimisation requires retention	On request	N/A	N/A
	Server	Application	Processing and storing of data. On CERTH premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	Until the end of the project	kvart granularity remain	CERTH PREMISES	CERTH PREMISES
	Citizen App	Application	Visualization of Data	all relevant values per pilot end-user	Until the end of the project	kvart granularity remain	N/A	N/A
Indoor Ambient conditions	Database	System	Cloud based component (ODFM)	All multisensors at pilot sites	For as long as the optimisation requires retention	On request	N/A	N/A
	Server	Application	Processing and storing of data. On CERTH premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	Until the end of the project	kvart granularity remain	CERTH PREMISES	CERTH PREMISES
	Citizen App	Application	Visualization of Data	all relevant values per pilot end-user	Until the end of the project	kvart granularity remain	N/A	N/A

Indoor Ambient conditions	Database	System	Cloud based component (ESCo tool - ECTs)	All multisensors at pilot sites	Until end of project	On request	N/A	N/A
Control actions (remote switching/change of device settings)	ODFM	System	Cloud based component (ODFM)	All controllable devices at pilot sites	As long as it takes to send the control actions to BIML	On request	N/A	N/A
Profiling data (occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flexibility profiles)	Database	System	Cloud based component (ODFM)	All prosumers at pilot sites	A day	On request	N/A	N/A
	Server	Application	Processing and storing of data. On CERTH premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	Until the end of the project	Max granularity remain	CERTH PREMISES	CERTH PREMISES
	Citizen App	Application	Visualization of Data	all relevant values per pilot end-user	Until the end of the project	Max granularity remain	N/A	N/A
Optimisation results	Database	System	Cloud based component (ODFM)	All prosumers at pilot sites	A day	On request	N/A	N/A
	Server	Application	Processing and storing of data. On CERTH premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	Until the end of the project	Max granularity remain	CERTH PREMISES	CERTH PREMISES
	Citizen App	Application	Visualization of Data	all relevant values per pilot end-user	Until the end of the project	Max granularity remain	N/A	N/A
Optimisation results	Database	System	Cloud based component (ECFM - ECTs)	All prosumers at pilot sites	A day	On request	N/A	N/A
Building assets static data	Database	System	Cloud based component (VPP manager - ECTs)	All prosumers at pilot sites	Until end of project	On request	N/A	N/A
Building assets static data	Database	System	Cloud based component (ESCo tool - ECTs)	All prosumers at pilot sites	Until end of project	On request	N/A	N/A
Profiling data (flexibility profiles)	Database	System	Cloud based component (ECFM, VPP manager, Vertical ECTs - ECTs)	All prosumers at pilot sites	A day	On request	N/A	N/A

Severity & Likelihood Assessment

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)		Asset	Severity at PA level		Severity at TC level		Likelihood at PA level		Likelihood at TC level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data					3				2
PossibleThreats									
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No lawfulness of processing	DER_Measurements	3	Moderate			2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Collection exceeding purpose	Indoor Ambient conditions	3	Moderate			2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unclear responsibilities for Data Processing.	Control actions (remote switching/change of device settings)	3	Moderate			1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The protection of data is compromised outside the European Economic Area (EEA).	Profiling data (occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flexibility profiles)	3	Moderate			2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below	Optimisation results	2	Limited			1	Negligible	
Inadequate information of the data subject					2				3
Possible Threats									
<input type="checkbox"/>	Incomplete information	DER_Measurements	2	Limited			3	Moderate	
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below	Indoor Ambient conditions	2	Limited			3	Moderate	
Violation of the data subject's rights					4				2
Possible Threats									
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Inability to execute individual rights (inspection rights)	Control actions (remote switching/change of device settings)	4	Significant			2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Prevention of objections	Profiling data (occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flexibility profiles)	3	Moderate			2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	A lack of transparency for automated individual decisions	Optimisation results	3	Moderate			2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Lack of correction of Personal Data								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of erasure of Personal Data								
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below								

Compliance violations in the contracts					0			1
Possible Threats								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Missing or incorrect contractual Data Protection clause							
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>							
Personal Data integrity loss					3			3
Possible Threats								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of quality of data for the purpose of use	<i>DER_Measurements</i>	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Inability to respond to requests for subject access, correction or deletion of data in a timely and satisfying manner.	<i>Indoor Ambient conditions</i>	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>	Building assets static data	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	
Damage to individual					0			1
Possible Threats								
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discrimination							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Identify Theft or Fraud							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Financial loss							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other significant economic or social disadvantage							
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>							

Residual Risk Level

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)		Step 6									
		Asset	Initial Severity at PA level	Residual Severity at PA level	Initial Severity at TC level	Residual Severity at TC level	Initial Likelihood at PA level	Residual Likelihood at PA level	Initial Likelihood at TC level	Residual Likelihood at TC level	
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data			Significant			4	3	Significant		4	1
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	DER_Measurements	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		2	Limited	1	Negligible
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	Indoor Ambient conditions	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		2	Limited	1	Negligible
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	Control actions (remote switching/change of device)	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		1	Negligible	1	Negligible
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Partitioning Personal Data	Profiling data (occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flex)	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		2	Limited	1	Negligible
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Encrypting Personal Data	Optimisation results	2	Limited	2	Limited		1	Negligible	1	Negligible
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Anonymizing Personal Data	Building assets static data	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		2	Limited	1	Negligible
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations	0	0					0			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data	0	0					0			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions	0	0					0			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose	0	0					0			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items	0	0					0			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed	0	0					0			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Destruction schedules for personal information	0	0	0				0	0		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals	0	0	0				0	0		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit	0	0	0				0	0		
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:	0	0	0				0	0		
Inadequate information of the data subject		0	0			2	2	0		3	2
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Informing data subjects Clear and consistent communication of purpose and goals of data collection	DER_Measurements	2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:	Indoor Ambient conditions	2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited
	Control actions (remote switching/change of device)		2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited
	Profiling data (occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flex)		2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited
	Optimisation results		2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited
	Building assets static data		2	Limited	2	Limited		3	Moderate	2	Limited

Violation of the data subject's rights		0	0			4	3	0			2	2
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	Violations (remote switching/change of devices)	4	Significant	3	Moderate		2	Limited	2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Permitting the exercise of the right to object	Occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, flex	3	Moderate	2	Limited		2	Limited	2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal	Optimisation results	3	Moderate	2	Limited		2	Limited	2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit	0	0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Obtaining the consent of data subjects	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right	0	0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR	0	0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to erase (right to be forgotten) according to article 17 of the GDPR	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:	0	0					0				
Compliance violations in the contracts		0	0			0	0	0			1	1
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Introduction automated controls on the data quality	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit	0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR	0	0	0				0	0			
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:	0	0	0				0	0			

Personal Data integrity loss		0	0			3	3	0			3	2
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	DER_Measurements	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives	Indoor Ambient conditions	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations	Building assets static data	3	Moderate	3	Moderate		3	Moderate	2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data		0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal		0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Introduction automated controls on the data quality		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, bad		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0					0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:		0					0				
Damage to individual		0	0			0	0	0			1	1
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Partitioning Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Encrypting Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anonymizing Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Tracing the activity on the IT system		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Combating malicious codes		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing software vulnerabilities		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing hardware vulnerabilities		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of computer communications networks		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of paper documents		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing vulnerabilities related to the circulation of paper documents		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of individuals		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items)							0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed							0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Destruction schedules for personal information		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:		0					0				

ANNEX II – DPIA (BIML-C-App)

Internal Team

DPIA will be performed by:	Option III	: the persons in charge of the application/system which is the target of the DPIA. This might especially apply in the case of SME's with limited resources.
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Actors & Assets

Asset	Actor Name (physical component)	Actor Type	Actor description (e.g. Where does Personal Data Processing Operations occur?)	How many data subjects for that Personal Data reside in each Actor instance?	Retention Time within Actor		Data Controller (physical person in the internal team)	Data Processor (physical person in the internal team)
					How long are they kept within the Actor?	How frequently are Personal Data accessed?		
Contextual Information data processing	Cloud Infrastructure	Application	Processing and storing of data. On que premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	5 years after the end of the project	kvat granularity remain	QUE IT department	QUE IT department
	Server	Application	Processing and storing of data. On CERTH premises	all relevant values for all pilot users	Until the end of the project	kvat granularity remain	CERTH PREMISES	CERTH PREMISES
	Citizen App	Application	Visualization of Data	all relevant values per pilot end-user	Until the end of the project	kvat granularity remain	N/A	N/A
Energy Exchange Data	Cloud Infrastructure	Application	processing of data for DR on distributed network	all power consumption/production values from all sites	foever	every 15 minutes	QUE IT department	QUE IT department

Severity & Likelihood Assessment

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)		Asset	Severity at PA level		Severity at TC level	Likelihood at PA level		Likelihood at TC level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data					4			2
Possible Threats		Contextual Information from raw data processing	4	Significant		2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No lawfulness of processing	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate		2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Collection exceeding purpose							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unclear responsibilities for Data Processing.							
<input type="checkbox"/>	The protection of data is compromised outside the European Economic Area (EEA).							
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below							
Inadequate information of the data subject					1			1
Possible Threats								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Incomplete information	Contextual Information from raw data processing	1	Negligible		2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below	Energy Exchange Data	1	Negligible		1	Negligible	
Violation of the data subject's rights					3			2
Possible Threats								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Inability to execute individual rights (inspection rights)	Contextual Information from raw data processing	3	Moderate		2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Prevention of objections	Energy Exchange Data	2	Limited		2	Limited	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	A lack of transparency for automated individual decisions							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of correction of Personal Data							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Lack of erasure of Personal Data							
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify below							

Compliance violations in the contracts					2		2
Possible Threats							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Missing or incorrect contractual Data Protection clause	Contextual Information from raw data processing	2	Limited		2	Limited
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>	Energy Exchange Data	2	Limited		1	Negligible
Personal Data integrity loss					3		3
Possible Threats							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of quality of data for the purpose of use	Contextual Information from raw data processing	3	Moderate		3	Moderate
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Inability to respond to requests for subject access, correction or deletion of data in a timely and satisfying manner.	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate		3	Moderate
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>						
Damage to individual					4		3
Possible Threats							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Discrimination	Contextual Information from raw data processing	4	Significant		3	Moderate
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Identify Theft or Fraud	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate		2	Limited
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Financial loss						
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other significant economic or social disadvantage						
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>						

Residual Risk Level

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)		Step 6												
		Asset	Initial Severity at PA level		Residual Severity at PA level		Initial Severity at TC level	Residual Severity at TC level	Initial Likelihood at PA level		Residual Likelihood at PA level		Initial Likelihood at TC level	Residual Likelihood at TC level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data		e.g. A/C_Load_Measurements	4	Significant	4	Significant	4	4	4	Significant	2	Limited	4	2
Possible Risk Treatment		external Information from raw data proces	4	Significant	1	Negligible				2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate	1	Negligible				2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Partitioning Personal Data	0	0						0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Encrypting Personal Data	0	0						0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Anonymizing Personal Data	0	0						0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations	0	0						0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items	0	0						0					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed	0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Destruction schedules for personal information	0	0	0					0	0				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals	0	0	0					0	0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit	0	0	0					0	0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify, below:</i>	0	0	0					0	0				
Inadequate information of the data subject		0	0					1	1	0			1	1
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0						0					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Informing data subjects Clear and consistent communication of purpose and goals of data collection	external Information from raw data proces	1	Negligible	1	Negligible			2	Limited	1	Negligible		
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify, below:</i>	Energy Exchange Data	1	Negligible	1	Negligible			1	Negligible	1	Negligible		

Violation of the data subject's rights						0	0			3	1	0			2	1
Possible Risk Treatment						0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	external Information from raw data proces	3	Moderate	1	Negligible						2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Permitting the exercise of the right to object	Energy Exchange Data	2	Limited	1	Negligible						2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Obtaining the consent of data subjects		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to erase (right to be forgotten) according to article 17 of the GDPR		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify, below:</i>		0									0				
Compliance violations in the contracts						0	0			2	1	0			2	1
Possible Risk Treatment						0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	external Information from raw data proces	2	Limited	1	Negligible						2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	Energy Exchange Data	2	Limited	1	Negligible						1	Negligible	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Introduction automated controls on the data quality		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR		0		0							0	0			
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify, below:</i>		0		0							0	0			
Personal Data integrity loss						0	0			3	1	0			3	1
Possible Risk Treatment						0	0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	external Information from raw data proces	3	Moderate	1	Negligible						3	Moderate	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate	1	Negligible						3	Moderate	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Introduction automated controls on the data quality		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR		0									0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify, below:</i>		0									0				

Damage to individual		0	0			4	2	0			3	2
Possible Risk Treatment		0	0									
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	external Information from raw data proces	4	Significant	2	Limited		0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Monitoring logical access controls	Energy Exchange Data	3	Moderate	1	Negligible		3	Moderate	2	Limited	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Partitioning Personal Data		0					2	Limited	1	Negligible	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Encrypting Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anonymizing Personal Data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Protecting Personal Data archives		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing Personal Data violations		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Tracing the activity on the IT system		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Combating malicious codes		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing software vulnerabilities		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing hardware vulnerabilities		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of computer communications networks		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of paper documents		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing vulnerabilities related to the circulation of paper documents		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reducing the vulnerabilities of individuals		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items)							0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed							0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Destruction schedules for personal information		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Audit		0					0				
<input type="checkbox"/>	If other, please specify, below:		0					0				

ANNEX III - Threats affecting Assets

Threat Category	Threat	Explanation of threat	Specific Energy industry examples of Supporting Asset vulnerabilities	Questions for guidance	Proposed mitigation strategies
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	No lawfulness of processing	To process Personal Data it is necessary to have a legal basis defined in Art.6 GDPR or the national Data Protection laws (e.g. consent of the data subject, contract with the data subject, documented legitimate interest of the Data Controller, legal requirements)		Is there a documented legal basis defined for the lawfulness of Data Processing?	Defining a legal basis for the process and controlling if the process follows that legal basis
	Collection exceeding purpose	More Personal Data is collected than what is necessary to achieve a specified purpose.	Collecting more detailed load profile data for the purpose of monthly billing, where much less detailed data would be sufficient to achieve the same objective.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What Personal Data do you need to collect for the purpose? 2. Is the collected data proportional to the purpose? 	Minimizing the amount of Personal Data. Active measure to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application for any other purpose
	Unclear responsibilities for Data Processing.	It is not clear to data subjects what parties are involved in the processing of data and their respective roles.	Installation organisation is acting as a subcontractor for the metering operator and is collecting data for the grid operator. The energy service company (ESCo) hires a third party to collect data to provide energy saving advice to the consumer.	<p>Are responsibilities clearly described and carried out for all parties?</p> <p>Is responsibility for Data Processing part of a sub-contractors contract?</p>	Informing data subjects Make a privacy policy, code of conduct or certify the processing of the data to be more transparent

	The protection of data is compromised outside the European Economic Area (EEA).	There is a risk that smart metering data may be at risk if sent outside of the EEA. Another risk is that Personal Data like metering data gives inside information about vital infrastructures in an unknown, maybe untruthful environment	Data Protection standards outside the EEA may not be secure and robust as those countries are not subject to the obligations within the GDPR. Foreign organisations use information about vital infrastructures and personal information to investigate people of interest.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you transfer the Personal Data outside the EEA? 2. To which country outside the EEA is the Personal Data transferred to? 3. Is the Personal Data transferred to a country that provides an adequate level of protection according to article 32 of GDPR? 4. How did you guarantee the protection of the Personal Data when transferred outside EEA? 5. Are all parties involved in implementation and operation established in the EU? 	Anonymizing Personal Data Limiting Personal Data transfer to countries that provide an adequate level of protection according to the article 32 of the GDPR Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items Not transferring the source data, but only the outcomes
Inadequate information of the data subject	Incomplete information	The information provided to the data subject on the purpose and use of data is not complete	Information provided to consumers only consists of usage data, information about other information (such as the ability to detect communication disruptions) gathered is not provided.	How did you notify the purpose of the processing operation of Personal Data to the consumers?	Informing data subjects Clear and consistent communication of purpose and goals of data collection
Violation of the data subject's rights	Inability to execute individual rights (inspection rights)	If data are going to be held by multiple Data Controllers, then consumers should have a means by which to access these data from multiple sources using a single subject access request.	Petrol station and organisation providing invoices work together to enable charging of vehicles in joint controllership. Individuals should be provided with easy means to get insight in the data collected (e.g. by a unified user access right).	1. Is a procedure in place to easily inform consumers about the use of his Personal Data?	Informing data subjects Obtaining the consent of data subjects Giving the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal

	Prevention of objections	Data subjects have the right to object to the processing of data. If they want to exercise this right it must be (technically) possible.	Consumers cannot opt out to reading of detailed energy load profiles because read-out schemes are not configurable: There are no technical or operational means to allow compliance with a data subject's objection.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is it possible to change the collection of Personal Data in the Smart Grid Use Case after the consumer's objection? 2. Can consumers object to processing of Personal Data use by certain technologies? 	Permitting the exercise of the right to object Make a privacy policy, code of conduct or certify the processing of the data to be more transparent
	A lack of transparency for automated individual decisions	Automated processing of Personal Data intended to evaluate certain personal aspects or conduct is used but the data subjects are not informed about the logic of the decision-making.	Remote disconnection is performed without providing clear explanation of the reasons to the user.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are consumers informed of automated information processing? 2. How are the consumers notified of automated individual decisions? 	Informing data subjects
	Lack of correction of Personal Data	There is no way for the data subject to initiate a correction of his data according to article 16 of the GDPR. The Data Controller and / or Data Processor are not sufficiently prepared to respond to such requests.	A personalized overview of Personal Data from the data subject cannot be corrected from the database that holds the data.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there processes to meet the consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion and correction? 2. Are you able to provide overview of data collected? 3. Are you able to correct the data on request? 	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal
	Lack of erasure of Personal Data	There is no way for the data subject to initiate	A personalized overview of Personal Data from the data subject cannot	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there processes to meet the consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion 	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right Allowing the exercise of the right to erase (right to be forgotten) according to article 17 of the GDPR

		an erasure of his data according to article 17 of the GDPR. The Data Controller and / or Data Processor are not sufficiently prepared to respond to such requests.	be erased from the database that holds the data.	and correction? 2. Are you able to provide overview of data collected? 3. Are you able to delete the data on request?	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his data, for example by a secured website portal
Compliance violations in the contracts	Missing or incorrect contractual Data Protection clause	It is required to have a Data Protection clause in contracts for Data Processing on behalf. The content of the Data Protection clause is legally required and different in the EU countries. There are additional requirements for Data Processors in third Countries.	To provide consumption data to the customers by internet platforms IT-provider gets into contact with these data as a Data Processor.	Are there Data Protection clauses and technical and organizational measures defined in the contract with the provider involved in the process?	Implementation of Data Protection clauses for Data Processing on behalf together with the procurement department
Personal Data integrity loss	Lack of quality of data for the purpose of use	If data is used for certain processes, it should be adequate.	For billing on a daily basis data should be registered on a daily basis. For disconnecting electricity supply the exact location (address) and reasons should be conclusive. Based upon wrong consumption data a wrong invoice is sent. A comma is used as a separator where a full-	1. Are automated input validation and reconciliation controls implemented? 2. How do you ensure data quality for the purpose of use? 3. Are there test procedures for data quality?	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data Introduction of automated controls on the data quality

	Inability to respond to requests for subject access, correction or deletion of data in a timely and satisfying manner.	The data is distributed across several business units and an integrated overview cannot be made within a short time frame.	stop is intended. This leads to wrong invoice. Metering data is stored and maintained by the technical department, reactions on commercial offers are stored at the commercial department, questions and answers are stored at the service department. Combining this data in one overview takes (a lot of) effort.	1. Are there processes to meet the consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion and correction? 2. Are you able to provide an overview of data collected? Are you able to provide what data is transferred to a third party? 3. Can an overview of what data is provided to whom be provided? 4. Are you able to delete the data on request?	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal.
Damage to Individual	Discrimination				
	Identify Theft or Fraud				
	Financial loss				
	Other significant economic or social disadvantage				

ANNEX II - Severity & Likelihood Scale

Severity	Negligible	Limited	Moderate	Significant	Maximum
Description	Identifying an individual using its Personal Data appears to be virtually impossible (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population on one meter reading). Data subjects either will not be affected or may encounter a few inconveniences, which they will overcome without any problem (time spent re-entering information, annoyances, irritations, etc.).	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be difficult but is possible in certain cases (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's 1-day history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter significant inconveniences, which they will be able to overcome despite a few difficulties (extra costs, denial of access to business services, fear, lack of understanding, stress, minor physical ailments, etc.).	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be common (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's 1-week history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter consequences, which they will be able to overcome (extra costs due to denial of access to business services, delay, fury, minor physical ailments, etc.).	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be relatively easy (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's history of meter readings of multiple days). Data subjects may encounter significant consequences, which they should be able to overcome albeit with serious difficulties (misappropriation of funds, blacklisting by banks, property damage, loss of employment, subpoena, worsening of state of health, etc.).	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be extremely easy (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter significant, or even irreversible, consequences, which they may not overcome (financial distress such as substantial debt or inability to work, long-term psychological or physical ailments, death, etc.).
Level of Severity	1	2	3	4	5

Likelihood	Negligible	Limited	Moderate	Significant	Maximum
Description	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets does not appear possible (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a badge reader and access code). Risk sources do not appear to have any special capabilities to carry out a Threat (e.g. software function creep by an individual acting without malicious intent and who has limited access privileges).	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be difficult (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a badge reader). The capabilities of Risks Sources to carry out a Threat are limited (e.g.: software function creep by a malicious individual with limited access privileges).	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be common (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a master key). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a Threat are common (e.g. software function creep by a malicious individual with limited administration privileges).	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be possible (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in offices that cannot be accessed without first checking in at reception). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a Threat are real and significant (e.g. software function creep by an individual acting without malicious intent and who has unlimited administration privileges).	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be extremely easy (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a lobby). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a threat are defined and unlimited (e.g. software function creep by a malicious individual with unlimited administration privileges).
Level of Likelihood	1	2	3	4	5